

CHARACTERISTICS OF ETHAMBUTOL OPTIC NEUROPATHY ON TUBERCULOSIS TREATMENT IN SANGLAH HOSPITAL DENPASAR

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ABSTRACT Background: Enforcement of ethambutol toxic optic neuropathy diagnosis uses visual examination, (relative afferent pupillary defect) RAPD, contrast sensitivity, colour vision, visual field, and patient complaints that are subjective so that an objective investigation is needed using visual evoked potential (VEP). **Method:** This study was a cross-sectional descriptive study in 30 pulmonary tuberculosis patients and were therefore referred to the pulmonology clinic of Public General Sanglah Hospital, Denpasar, from May 13 to August 13, 2018, based on medical record data. This study aims to determine the characteristics of patients with ethambutol toxic optic neuropathy at the pulmonology clinic of Public General Sanglah Hospital Denpasar. **Results:** We reported 30 patients, 19 were male and 11 female, mean age 33 years, visual acuity disorder and red-green dyschromatopsia seven people, and optic nerve lesions five people. Impaired visual acuity, colour dyschromatopsia, and VEP abnormalities found in patients with ethambutol treatment for five months. **Conclusions:** Impaired visual acuity, colour dyschromatopsia, and optic nerve (ON) lesion were obtained five months of treatments.

KEYWORDS VEP, neuropathy optics, ethambutol, tuberculosis

Introduction

Ethambutol has been used to treat tuberculosis since 1960, and visual disturbances have shown since this drug introduced.[1] Ethambutol provides potential and severe adverse effects on the eyes. Ocular toxicity in the form of toxic optic neuritis or retrobulbar neuritis that can affect one eye or both eyes. The most common side effects of ethambutol are optical nerve fibres, which can cause blurred vision, decreased vision, visual field defects, central scotoma, and dyschromatopsia. The mechanism

of occurrence is still unknown, but it is thought to be due to the zinc-chelating effect of ethambutol. The incidence of toxicity obtained from various studies varies from 0.5 to 35%.[2]

Many studies that explain the toxicity of ethambutol to tuberculosis patients, but the number of samples used is still small. The purpose of this study was to determine the characteristics of ethambutol toxic optic neuropathy in pulmonary tuberculosis patients.

Methods

This study was a cross-sectional descriptive design of all pulmonary tuberculosis patients undergoing treatment at the Pulmonary Polyclinic of Sanglah General Hospital, Denpasar. Data collection was carried out from 13 May to 13 August 2018. Data analysis was done using version 20 Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) data processing software. The inclusion criteria for this study were all patients with pulmonary tuberculosis pa-

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Table 1 Demographics of the 30 patients with ethambutol optic neuropathy.

Variable		n=30	Percent (%)
Age (years)	Minimum-maximum	20-72	
	Mean	33.5 (±11.9)	
Sex	Male	19	63.3
	Female	11	36.7
Education	Junior High School	2	6.7
	Senior High School	28	93.3
Occupation	Student	3	10
	Private employees	11	36.7
	Entrepreneurs	16	53.3
Hometown	Denpasar	15	50
	Badung	4	13.3
	Kuta	2	6.7
	Negara	1	3.3
	Gianyar	2	6.7
Others		6	20
Anti-TB drug	TB categories 1	12	40
	TB categories 2	18	60
Duration Anti-TB drug	One month	1	3.3
	Two months	12	40
	Three months	2	6.7
	Four months	0	0
	Five months	6	20
	Six months	4	13.3
	Seven months	1	3.3
	Eight months	1	3.3
	Nine months	2	6.7
>Nine months	1	3.3	

Table 1. (Continue).

Variable		n=30	Percent (%)
Visus Ocular Dextra (OD)	Normal	23	76.7
	Disturbance	7	23.3
Visus Ocular Sinistra (OS)	Normal	23	76.7
	Disturbance	7	23.3
Dyschromatopsia	Yes	7	23.3
	No	23	76.7
Visual filed disorder	Yes	0	0
	No	30	100
RAPD	Yes	0	0
	No	30	100
Contrast Sensitivity	Normal	30	100
	Abnormal	0	0
Funduscopy	Normal	30	100
	Abnormal	0	0
OCT	Normal	30	100
	Abnormal	0	0
REP	Normal	25	83.3
	Abnormal	5	16.7

tients who received ethambutol in the Lung Hospital Polyclinic Sanglah Denpasar.

The exclusion criteria for the study subjects were: Patients with pulmonary tuberculosis without medical record data and incomplete examination and all pulmonary tuberculosis patients who refused to take the study. Samples were taken continuous using consecutive sampling from the medical records of patients diagnosed with pulmonary tuberculosis at Sanglah General Hospital, Denpasar. The instruments used consisted of the Philippine National Registry for EMB-Related Toxic-Optic Neuropathy Questionnaire and the data collection sheet was used to record the patient's baseline data. The study began by taking data sources through the medical records of all pulmonary tuberculosis patients who received ethambutol at the Lung Hospital Polyclinic Sanglah Denpasar from 13 May to 13 August 2018. Then carried out recording the patient's identity, history, and complaints of disease. Then a neuro-ophthalmology examination, VEP examination, and Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) were performed. The results of neuro-ophthalmology, VEP, and OCT examinations were recorded and analyzed. After all the data obtained when an analysis is performed using SPSS version 20 software, then conclusions and explanations are prepared from the results of data analysis.

Table 2 Clinical manifestations of the five patients with ethambutol optic neuropathy.

Parameter		n=5
Age (mean & SD)		46.8 (±16,4)
Sex	Male	4
	Female	1
Anti-Tb Drug Categories	Type 1	0
	Type 2	5
Duration of administration	five months	1
	six months	1
	nine months	1
	>nine months	1
Latency P100 OZ (mean and SD)	Right eye	114 (±4.5)
	Left eye	121.8 (±11.2)
Conclusion VEP	Right ON temporal lesion	1
	Right ON post chiasma lesion	1
	NO post chiasma bilateral lesion	1
	NO bilateral lesion	2

Results

This study used a cross-sectional descriptive design with a total sample of 30 patients. The patient's demographic characteristics differed according to age, sex, education, occupation, hometown, and clinical features, anti-TB drug categories, duration of drug administration, sharp visual impairment, colour vision, visual field, contrast sensitivity, RAPD, funduscopy, OCT, and VEP as shown in table 1.

Table.1 shows the essential characteristics of pulmonary tuberculosis patients who received ethambutol drugs (n = 30), where the mean age was 33.5 (SD ± 11.9) with the lowest 20 years and the highest 72 years, male sex 19 people (63, 3%), the most education is high school as many as 28 people (93.3%), the most work is entrepreneurship as many as 16 people (53.3%), and most of them reside in Denpasar.

Clinically, from 30 TB patients there were 18 people using OAT category (60%), the highest duration of treatment for two months was 12 people (40%), OD and OS vision problems were seven people (23.3%), colour vision disorders were seven people (23.3%), and abnormal VEPs were five people (16.7%). In this study, there were no patients with visual field, RAPD, funduscopy, and OCT images disorders.

Based on VEP conclusions, right ocular nerve lesions temporal region, right post chiasma ocular nerve lesion, and bilateral post chiasma optic nerve lesion as many as one people (20%) and bilateral ocular nerve lesion as much as two people (40%). Based on gender, subjects with abnormal VEP were four people (80%) men and one person (20%) women. Based on the duration of administration of ethambutol, all subjects with ethambutol toxic optic neuropathy received ethambutol for ≥ five months.

Discussion

Based on the results of the above research, from 30 patients in Sanglah General Hospital Denpasar who received ethambutol, the mean age was 33.5 years (SD ± 11.9), and the age range was 20-72 years. Another study found an average age of 26.5 years (SD ± 9.5) with the majority of subjects in the age group 15-30 years.[3] Elderly is said to be one of the factors that increase the risk of experiencing visual disturbances due to ethambutol.[3] Male research subjects - there are 19 people (63.3%) more than women who number 11 (36.7%), and this result is consistent with the research of Yusriani et al. (2012) in Medan where there were more male research subjects, namely there were 12 people (52.2%) compared to women who numbered 11 people (47.8%).[4] Based on the latest education of the research subjects, it obtained from 30 patients, most of whom had a high school education, 28 people (93.3%) and the remaining 2 people (6.7%) have a junior secondary education background and this is consistent with the research of Yusriani et al.(2012) where the highest level of senior secondary education background is 13 people (56.5%) compared to junior high school (13.1%) and bachelor (30.4%).[4]

In this study, ethambutol optic toxic neuropathy was five patients(16.7%). The prevalence of ethambutol toxic optic neuropathy is unknown but based on the literature the incidence varied between 0.5-35%.[6] Based on age, the mean age of patients with ethambutol toxic optic neuropathy is 46.8 (SB ± 16.4) years with a range of 29-72 years and in the previous study found an average age of 76.8 (SD ± 7.2) years with a variety of 59-85 years.[7] Old age is said to increase the risk of having ethambutol toxic optic neuropathy, but until now there is no reliable evidence.

Based on the sex, the majority of patients with ethambutol toxic optic neuropathy are male, namely as many as four people (80%) and the remaining women are one person (20%) and this result is in accordance with previous studies by Chen et al. (2015) where the majority of the study subjects were ethambutol toxic optic neuropathy of the male sex (81.25%). [7] All patients with ethambutol toxic optical neuropathy (100%) received category 2, and this is probably due to the essential characteristics of the subject. Most of the research (60%) got anti-TB drug category 2.

Based on the duration of treatment, two people (40%) received ethambutol for two months, and the remaining one person (20%) received ethambutol for 6, 9 and 14 months. These results are consistent with Chan and Kwok's research which states that ethambutol intoxication manifestations occur most often between the 3rd and 5th months of treatment, although in some cases these manifestations only appear after the 12th to the 3rd year since administration. [8]

On VEP examination, the average latency of P100 OZ was 114 ms (SD \pm 4.5) in the right eye and 121.8 ms (SD \pm 1.1) in the left eye and this result was consistent with Yiannikas et al. (1983) where there was an increase in P100 latency of more than 10 ms above the average value. [5] Measurement of P100 latency on VEP can detect the presence of ethambutol optical neuritis early. [9] Other studies mention the duration of ethambutol administration associated with prolongation of P100.20 latency in VEP conclusions, two people (40%) experienced bilateral optic nerve lesions, and each person (20%) had temporal right optic nerve lesion, right post-chiasm ocular nerve lesion, and post-chiasma ocular nerve lesions. [10] These results are by following with the literature which states that the most common neuropathy due to ethambutol toxicity is retrobulbar optic neuritis with axial, peri-axial, and mixed fibre involvement. [8]

Conclusion

Impaired visual acuity, colour dyschromatopsia, and optic nerve lesion were obtained five months of treatments.

Competing Interests

There were no financial supports or relationships between authors and any organization or professional bodies that could pose any conflict of interest.

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